

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

THE MEANING AND METHODS OF TRANSPORT DEMAND FORECAST

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Abstract

Transport is the vital blood stream of every society, every country and the world in global frameworks. The forecast of the transport delay is of great importance and can be done by neighborhoods in urban areas, cities, regions and entire countries, such a forecasting tool is the world-leading PTV VISION VISUM software, which contains several ways in which the forecast can be performed. Forecasted travel demand is based on data on future land use, future population and economic structure and the future transport supply system.^[1] In this paper, the methods for the example of the city of Bitola will be shown. In this paper, the three ways of forecasting the transport acceleration will be shown, with a detailed presentation of the accompanying steps for achieving the set goal, that is, forecasting. The forecast for the next 10 years will be shown for the city of Bitola, for private and public transportation.

Keywords: methods, transport, forecast, software, city.

Introduction

Transportation forecasting is the attempt of estimating the number of vehicles or people that will use a specific transportation facility in the future. For instance, a forecast may estimate the number of vehicles on a planned road or bridge, the ridership on a railway line, the number of passengers visiting an airport, or the number of ships calling on a seaport. Traffic forecasting begins with the collection of data on current traffic. This traffic data is combined with other known data, such as population, employment, trip rates, travel costs, etc., to develop a traffic demand model for the current situation. Feeding it with predicted data for population, employment, etc. results in estimates of future traffic, typically estimated for each segment of the transportation infrastructure in question, e.g., for each roadway segment or railway station. The current technologies facilitate the access to dynamic data, big data, etc., providing the opportunity to develop new algorithms to improve greatly the predictability and accuracy of the current estimations.

Traffic forecasts are used for several key purposes in transportation policy, planning, and engineering: to calculate the capacity of infrastructure, e.g., how many lanes a bridge should have; to estimate the financial and social viability of projects, e.g., using cost–benefit analysis and social impact assessment; and to calculate environmental impacts, e.g., air pollution and noise.^[3]

Transportation demand forecasts traditionally follow a four-step sequential model first implemented in the 1950s.^[4]

The forecast can be made by neighborhoods in urban areas, cities, regions and entire countries. Today, the development of informatics and computer technology has made a turn in traffic engineering, so calculations and forecasts are made through modern software tools and packages, which enable fast, accurate and

high-quality plans and projects. One such software tool is PTV VISION VISUM, which uses the standard four-stage forecast model.^[5] PTV Vision VISUM is used in a large number of traffic studies in almost all cities of the world, here we would single out the most famous traffic studies for Stockholm, Kranj, Germany, Brežice, Mozirje in the Republic of Slovenia, traffic study for the city of Bitola in R. Macedonia.^[2]

This paper will describe the methods offered by this software for forecasting the transport demand at the city level, the subject of the case being the city of Bitola.^[6]

Methods of transport demand forecast

After creating the traffic network, zoning the area, creating the demand model, the last and most important part is the transport demand forecast for the next few years. It can be carried out in several ways:

- estimated values for the attribute;
- creation of a new matrix;
- inhabitants - rise by a factor;^[7]

Estimated values for the attribute

This method of forecasting takes into account the increase in population. To be able to use this method, it is necessary to estimate the number of inhabitants. For each zone, in addition to the other defined attributes, the inhabitants attribute is entered. The assessment is made from previous information, factors, rates, etc. The first forecast method will be shown in the following images.

The Zones tool and the Edit mode command should be active, the zone in which we want to enter the estimated values should be selected, right-click and select User defined attribute, and in the residents attribute, we correct it and enter a new estimated value. It is done for each zone separately. It is shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 4 Selection of the 1Cn1 matrix

After we have chosen the matrix, we go to the next steps to define its parameters. We go to Parameters-Coefficient, write the coefficient and click OK. with that, the forecast step with this method is completed, and we can see the forecasted sizes after we click Start procedure sequence. This is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5 Input of a coefficient of the combined matrix with vectors for forecasting transport demand Inhabitants - rise by a factor

This method of forecasting is based on the use of the home-work matrix, i.e. 1Cn1, because those trips are the most numerous. We go with Overview- Matrices- 1Cn1- Projection. A new window opens where it is necessary to enter the increase factor, if we estimate that in the coming years we will have an increase in transport demand, then we take a factor greater than 1, if due to certain circumstances, consequences, migrations, the number of trips to a certain area for the following period decreased, then we use a factor smaller than 1, that is, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, and so on.

Fig. 6 View of the location of the Projection

A new window opens where we choose Multiply with factor to be active and we choose to do the calculations on the entire matrix with For the entire matrix active. In the field Parameters for reference type "entire matrix" factor we define the growth factor, in this case we choose growth factor 1.2. Display in Figure 7.

Fig. 7 Input of increase factor 1.2

In order to see the forecasted sizes, click on the Start procedure sequence tool. Figure 8 shows the predicted sizes for the city of Bitola, with a growth factor of 1.2.

Fig. 8 Forecasted sizes for the city of Bitola with a growth factor of 1.2

This way of forecasting also offers instead of a growth factor, to select an attraction factor, a production factor, and a combined attraction and production factor for each zone respectively. This is shown in Figure 9.[8]

Fig. 9 Selection of other factors with which the forecast of transport demand would be carried out

Conclusion

We can conclude from this paper that forecasting has always been a challenge for traffic engineers. With the development of information technology, this activity is solved through modern software tools and packages, such as the world-leading tool PTV VISION VISUM, and its possibilities offered for forecasting the transport demand in a given area in the following years. We can conclude that this software requires a lot of data to feed it for good output results. It is necessary to have a broad knowledge of all the influencing factors that directly or indirectly have an impact on the increase or decrease of transport demand. Depending on the type of data we have, we can adapt to the wide selection of forecasts offered by this software, so if we know what the number of inhabitants will be in the future, i.e. we estimate, then we can use the first method, while the second method using the homework matrix, we make a new matrix combined with a vector and coefficient. While the third way allows us to forecast the most numerous matrix with a growth factor, an attraction factor, a production factor, or combined. By understanding the current problems and applying different methods and plans, we arrive at the forecast for the future situation, ie forecast. It occurs in all pores of human activities, the biggest reason for forecasting is that it allows planning. The process of trip forecasting is at the heart

of urban transportation planning. Travel forecasting models are used to project future traffic and are the basis for determining the need for new road capacity, changes in transit services, and changes in policies and land use patterns. With the realization of this research, directions are opened for new further research, both for cities with a larger number of inhabitants with intense traffic loads, and for considering another type of transport demand and their application.

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